

Stereocontrolled synthesis of β -lactams via Staudinger reaction between phenoxyketenes and chiral imines

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Chiral Schiff bases derived from esters of valine and alanine have been shown to be useful intermediates for the stereoselective synthesis of β -lactams. Staudinger reaction between these compounds and phenoxyketenes, generated *in situ*, from the corresponding acid chlorides in the presence of triethylamine, provides a mixture of diastereomeric *cis*- β -lactams. Attempts have been made to separate them using column chromatography and their ratios determined through ^1H NMR data.

During the past twenty years asymmetric synthesis has forged to the forefront of organic chemistry. Ingenious synthetic methodologies that employ members of the 'chiral carbon pool', comprise a significant portion of this technology. To the organic chemist, this chiral pool, which is composed mainly of naturally occurring amino acids, terpenes, sugars and carbohydrates, is an invaluable source of stereochemically pure molecules. We limited our study to a specific class of compounds, the α -amino acids, for the generation of chiral intermediates and β -lactams.

Stereocontrolled synthesis of β -lactams continues to be an area of intense activity¹. The periodic discovery of new β -lactam antibiotics in nature sustains the interest of synthetic and medicinal chemists². Moreover, the strain energy associated with this heterocyclic system has also been exploited to provide useful synthetic building blocks³. 2-Azetidinones have also been used in ring expansion reactions for the synthesis of nine-membered heterocycles⁴. Highly stereoselective synthetic methods leading to optically pure β -lactams with a variety of substituents have been described⁵. In view of the growing interest in biological activities of the unnatural enantiomers, we describe here a pathway to non-classical optically active β -lactams, which can serve as synthons for natural products⁶.

This work involves the use of inherent chirality of an amino acid to induce asymmetry in a reaction that would normally be asymmetrically biased. Our strategy involves the synthesis of monocyclic β -lactams using L-amino acids as chiral components, whose absolute stereochemistry is already established. The carboxylic acid group can easily be converted to an ester by standard esterification techniques and the amine function can be used to prepare the required imines.

Results and Discussion

A single key step of synthesis, the cycloaddition of ketene to imine introduces simultaneously two asymmetric centres in the final products. However, only one racemate is obtained owing to the exclusive *cis*-stereospecificity of the cycloaddition. So we planned the stereochemical course of the asymmetric [2+2]cycloaddition by using a series of chiral Schiff bases derived from esters of valine and alanine. Earlier work⁷ suggests that when the Schiff base is derived from an optically active amine and an achiral aldehyde, the level of diastereoselectivity varies. But when optically active aldehyde and achiral amine are employed for preparing Schiff base, annelation reaction is totally stereospecific. Valine and alanine ester hydrochlorides/tosylates were prepared by usual procedures and were reacted with aldehydes in the presence of triethylamine in dichloromethane to furnish imines **2** in high yields. Reaction of imines **2** with phenoxyacetyl chlorides in the presence of triethylamine resulted into the diastereomeric mixture of two *cis*- β -lactams **3** (Scheme 1).

Compounds **3(i)** and **3(ii)** are formed in nearly equal amounts as calculated from ^1H NMR spectra of the crude product (d.e. 6%). Four distinct doublets for the β -lactam protons appeared at δ 5.15, 5.40, 5.55, 5.65 with *J* 5.0 Hz in each pair, confirming *cis*-orientation of C_3 - C_4 hydrogens in both the diastereomers. The observed lack of diastereofacial selectivity during cycloaddition is probably due to planar geometry of the chiral imine **2**. This provides equal ease of access from both the faces resulting in annelation without strong diastereoselectivity during formation of new chiral centres C_3 and C_4 of the β -lactam nucleus.

In order to investigate the effect of achiral aldehydes on the stereospecificity, β -lactams **3b-i** were synthesised by annelating respective chiral imines **2b-i** derived from vari-

Scheme 1

ously substituted aldehydes. The diastereomeric mixture of *cis*- β -lactams was obtained in poor diastereomeric excess (d.e. 6–10%). The absolute configuration of the two diastereomers are assigned tentatively on the basis of ¹H NMR spectra as 4a,b.

This is based on chemical shift of C₄-H appearing downfield in 4a than in 4b which can be attributed to the effect of lone-pair on nitrogen on the former.

Next, we prepared a Schiff base 6 chiral from aminoalcohol 5. Hydroxy group in 6 was protected as silylether and the resulting compound was annelated with phenoxyketene which also produced a diastereomeric mixture of *cis*- β -lactams (7)(i) and 7(ii) (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

Lastly, we thought of eliminating chiral centre at C₄ to see the effect on the diastereoselectivity. We took dithiocarbamate 8 as the starting material and transformed to iminodithiocarbamate 9. The cycloaddition reaction of 9 with phenoxyacetyl chloride and triethylamine yielded *cis*- β -lactams 10 as diastereomeric mixture. The diastereomeric mixture could not be resolved into individual diastereomers by silica gel chromatography using various solvent systems (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected. Solvents and reagents were purified by conventional methods. The petroleum ether used was the fraction boiling at 60–80°. Column chromatography was carried out on silica gel (60–120 mesh). IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 377 spectrophotometer and ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) on a Varian EM-390 (90 MHz)/EM-360 (60 MHz) instrument using TMS as internal standard. The elemental analyses (C, N, H) were performed in Microanalytical Section of Regional Sophisticated Instrument Centre, Panjab University, Chandigarh, using a Carlo Erba Strumantazone No. 1106-R/AS-23 analyzer.

L-Valine ester hydrochloride (**1a-f**) : A mixture of *L*-valine (5.0 g, 0.042 mol) and absolute ethanol (50 ml) was saturated with anhyd. HCl and then refluxed for 2 h. Removal of solvent under vacuum gave thick liquid which was crystallized to yield the title compound (85%), m.p. 102–104°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +6.6^\circ$ ($c = 2$, H_2O).

L-Alanine ester hydrochloride (**1g**) : A mixture of *L*-alanine (5.0 g, 0.056 mol) and absolute alcohol (50 ml) was saturated with anhyd. HCl and then refluxed for 2 h. Removal of solvent under vacuum gave **1g** as crystalline solid (80%), m.p. 60–61°.

Amino acid benzylester p-toluenesulfonate (**1h-i**). *General procedure* : A mixture of amino acid (125 mmol), *p*-toluenesulfonic acid monohydrate and benzyl alcohol (50 ml) taken in benzene (25 ml) was refluxed and the liberated water was removed azeotropically by means of Dean-Stark receiver. The resulting solution was cooled to room temperature and ether (250 ml) added. After standing overnight in the refrigerator, the crystalline product was filtered, (90%) : **1h**, m.p. 158–159°, **1i**, 170–171°.

Ethyl 2-(s-methylthiocarbamoyl)propionate (**8**) : To a well stirred mixture of carbon disulfide (3.8 g, 50.0 mmol) in THF (50 ml) were added *L*-alanine ethyl ester hydrochloride (**1g**; 7.675 g, 50.0 mol), water (50 ml) and potassium carbonate (7.590 g, 55 mmol). After 15 min, methyl iodide (7.810 g, 55 mmol) was added dropwise at low temperature and the solution stirred for 0.5 h. The reaction mixture was diluted with diethyl ether and washed with water. The organic layer was separated and dried. The removal of solvent gave **8** (76%), oil (Found : C, 40.4; H, 6.3; N, 6.5. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_2\text{S}_2$ calcd. for : C, 40.5; H, 6.3; N, 6.7%); ν_{max} 1750 (ester CO), 3320 cm^{-1} (NH); δ 1.40 (3H, t, $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 1.60 (3H, d, CHCH_3), 2.65 (3H, s, SCH_3), 4.25 (2H, q, $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 5.15 (1H, m, CH), 8.55 (1H, br, NH exchangeable with D_2O).

Schiff bases (**2a-g**). *General procedure* : A solution of

triethylamine (2.220 g, 0.022 mol) in dry dichloromethane (15 ml) was added dropwise to a well stirred mixture of *L*-valine ethyl ester hydrochloride (**1a-g**; 3.630 g, 0.02 mol) and benzaldehyde (2.120 g, 0.02 mol) in dry dichloromethane (50 ml) at 0°. After stirring overnight at room temperature, the reaction mixture was washed with dilute aqueous sodium metabisulfite solution, then with brine and dried. Removal of the solvent afforded the Schiff bases : **2a** (75%), oil, $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -68.25^\circ$ ($c = 1.78\%$ MeOH, 22.2°) (Found : C, 72.0; H, 8.1; N, 6.0. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}_2$ calcd. for : C, 72.0; H, 8.2; N, 6.0%); ν_{max} 1660 (CN), 1735 cm^{-1} (ester CO); δ 0.95 (6H, m, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1.30 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3), 2.45 (1H, m, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 3.85 (1H, d, NCH), 4.30 (2H, q, CH_2CH_3), 7.50–8.15 (5H, m, ArH), 8.45 (1H, s, $\text{HC}=\text{N}$); **g** (70%), oil (Found : C, 70.1; H, 7.2; N, 6.8. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_2$ calcd. for : C, 70.2; H, 7.3; N, 6.8%); ν_{max} 1660 (CN), 1735 cm^{-1} (ester CO); δ 1.25 (3H, t, $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 1.50 (3H, d, CHCH_3), 3.70 (1H, m, NCH), 4.22 (2H, q, CH_2CH_3), 8.02–7.34 (5H, m, ArH), 8.40 (1H, s, $\text{HC}=\text{N}$).

Schiff bases (**2h-i**) : To a suspension (50 mmol) of amino acid benzyl ester *p*-toluene sulfonate (**1h-i**) in chloroform (75 ml) at 0–5°, triethylamine (5 g, 50 mmol) was added with stirring over a period of 10 min. After the addition of absolute alcohol (100 ml), the mixture was allowed to stand for 10 min, and then the precipitated triethyl ammonium *p*-toluene sulfonate was filtered off. To the filtrate were added piperonal (7.5 g, 50 mmol) and triethylamine (5 g, 50 mmol) and the mixture was stirred for 4 h at low temperature. The mixture was then washed with brine and water. The organic layer was dried and the solvent removed in vacuo to afford the required Schiff bases (oil, 60%).

Schiff base 6 : A mixture of *L*-2-aminobutanol **5** (2.0 g, 0.022 mol) and piperonal (3.370 g, 0.022 mol) in presence of catalytic amount of *p*-toluene sulfonic acid was refluxed in dry benzene (50 ml) using Dean-Stark water separator. The reaction was monitored by TLC. Removal of benzene afforded an oil which on trituration with light petroleum gave **6** (80%), m.p. 60–61° (Found : C, 65.0; H, 6.8; N, 6.1. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_3$ calcd. for : C, 65.1; H, 6.8; N, 6.3%); ν_{max} 1640 (CN), 3190 cm^{-1} (OH); δ 0.85 (3H, t, CH_3), 1.60 (2H, m, C- CH_2), 2.25 (1H, s, OH), 3.10 (1H, m, NCH), 3.70 (2H, d, CH_2OH), 5.90 (2H, s, OCH_2O), 6.60–7.30 (3H, m, ArH), 8.05 (1H, s, $\text{HC}=\text{N}$).

Schiff base 9 : Ethyl 2-(*s*-methylthiocarbamoyl)propionate **8** (4.14 g, 0.002 mol) and methyl iodide (6.350 g, 0.05 mol) was dissolved in THF (50 ml). Sodium hydride (0.960 g, of a 51% mineral oil suspension, 0.02 mol) was added in small portions, so as to avoid foaming. After 10 min, the solution was diluted with diethyl ether (10 ml) and then

washed with water. The organic layer was separated, dried and evaporated to give an oil, which was chromatographed over neutral alumina using dichloromethane as an eluent to give the bismethylthioimine **9** (65%) (Found : C, 43.4; H, 6.7; N, 6.1. $C_8H_{15}NO_2S_2$ calcd. for : C, 43.4; H, 6.8; N, 6.3%; ν_{max} 1640 (CN), 1750 cm^{-1} (ester CO); δ 1.25 (3H, t, $COOCH_2CH_3$), 1.40 (3H, d, CH- CH_3), 2.45 (3H, s, SCH_3), 2.60 (3H, s, SCH_3), 4.35 (3H, m, $COOCH_2CH_3$, CH).

β -Lactams (3a-e, g-i, 10). *General procedure* : Phenoxyacetyl chloride (1.705 g, 0.01 mol) in dry dichloromethane (15 ml) was added dropwise to a well stirred mixture of imine (**2a-e, g-i, 9**; 2.330 g, 0.01 mol) and triethylamine (50 ml) at low temperature. After stirring overnight at room temperature (25°), the reaction mixture was washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate (10%), brine and dried. Removal of solvent provided β -lactams.

1H NMR of the crude product showed it to be the diastereomeric mixture of two *cis*- β -lactams. These were separated by chromatography on neutral alumina/silica gel using light petroleum : dichloromethane (9 : 1) as eluent. Only **3a(i)** could be obtained in pure form having $[\alpha]_D = -30.05^\circ$ ($c = 0.1\%$ MeOH, 22.2°); **3a** (65%) (Found : C, 71.8; H, 6.8; N, 3.6. $C_{22}H_{25}NO_4$ calcd. for : C, 71.9; H, 6.8; N, 3.8%; ν_{max} 1760 cm^{-1} (β -lactam CO); **3a(i)**, m.p. 57°, δ 0.80 (6H, t, $CH(CH_3)_2$), 1.28 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3), 1.95 (1H, m, $CH(CH_3)_2$), 4.25 (3H, q, CH_2CH_3 , NCH), 5.35 (1H, d, J 5.5 Hz, C_4 -H), 5.60 (1H, d, J 5.5 Hz, C_3 -H), 6.8–7.65 (10H, m, ArH); **3a(ii)**, m.p. 62–63°, δ 0.95 (6H, m, $CH(CH_3)_2$), 1.35 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3), 2.65 (1H, m, $CH(CH_3)_2$), 4.15 (2H, q, J 6 Hz, CH_2CH_3 , NCH), 5.35 (1H, d, J 5.5 Hz C_4 -H), 5.60 (1H, d, J 5.5 Hz, C_3 -H), 6.8–7.65 (10H, m, ArH); **3b** (65%) (i : ii 3 : 2), m.p. 70–75° (Found : C, 67.0; H, 6.1; N, 3.4. $C_{23}H_{25}NO_6$ calcd. for : C, 67.1; H, 6.1; N, 3.4%; ν_{max} 1760 cm^{-1} (β -lactam CO); **3b(i)**, δ 1.20 (9H, m, $COOCH_2CH_3$, $CH(CH_3)_2$), 2.10 (1H, m, $CH(CH_3)_2$), 4.15 (3H, m, $COOCH_2CH_3$, NCH), 5.30 (1H, d, J 5.5 Hz, C_4 -H), 5.55 (1H, d, J 5.5 Hz, C_3 -H), 6.05 (2H, s, OCH_2O), 6.75–7.55 (8H, m, ArH); **3b(ii)**, δ 1.20 (9H, m, $COOCH_2CH_3$, $CH(CH_3)_2$), 2.65 (1H, m, $CH(CH_3)_2$), 4.15 (3H, m, $COOCH_2CH_3$, NCH), 4.95 (1H, d, J 5.5 Hz, C_4 -H), 5.55 (1H, d, J 5.5 Hz, C_3 -H), 6.05 (2H, s, OCH_2O), 6.75–7.55 (8H, m, ArH); **3c** (70%) (i : ii 3 : 2), m.p. 76–80° (Found : C, 67.3; H, 6.8; N, 3.0. $C_{24}H_{29}NO_6$ calcd. for : C, 67.4; H, 6.8; N, 3.2%; ν_{max} 1740 cm^{-1} (β -lactam CO); **3c(i)**, δ 1.10 (9H, m, $COOCH_2CH_3$, $CH(CH_3)_2$), 2.0 (1H, m, $CH(CH_3)_2$), 3.95 (6H, s, 2*- OCH_3), 4.05 (1H, d, NCH), 4.25 (2H, q, $COOCH_2CH_3$), 5.25 (1H, d, J 5.5 Hz, C_4 -H), 5.55 (1H, d, J 5.5 Hz, C_3 -H), 6.75–7.35 (8H, m, ArH); **3c(ii)**, δ 1.10

(9H, m, $COOCH_2CH_3$, $CH(CH_3)_2$), 2.65 (1H, m, $CH(CH_3)_2$), 3.90 (6H, s, 2*- OCH_3), 4.05 (1H, d, NCH), 4.25 (2H, q, $COOCH_2CH_3$), 4.95 (1H, d, J 5.5 Hz, C_4 -H), 5.55 (1H, d, J 5.5 Hz, C_3 -H), 6.75–7.35 (8H, m, ArH); **3d** (72%) (i : ii 11 : 9), m.p. 70–74° (Found : C, 69.4; H, 6.8; N, 3.5. $C_{23}H_{27}NO_5$ calcd. for : C, 69.5; H, 6.8; N, 3.5%; ν_{max} 1765 cm^{-1} (β -lactam CO); **3d(i)**, δ 1.30 (9H, m, $COOCH_2CH_3$, $CH(CH_3)_2$), 1.95 (1H, m, $CH(CH_3)_2$), 3.95 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.35 (3H, t, NCH, $COOCH_2CH_3$), 5.30 (1H, d, J 5.5 Hz, C_4 -H), 5.60 (1H, d, J 5.5 Hz, C_3 -H), 6.85–7.45 (9H, m, ArH); **3d(ii)**, δ 1.05 (9H, m, $COOCH_2CH_3$, $CH(CH_3)_2$), 2.60 (1H, m, $CH(CH_3)_2$), 3.85 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.00 (1H, d, NCH), 4.25 (2H, q, $COOCH_2CH_3$), 5.0 (1H, d, J 5.5 Hz, C_4 -H), 5.55 (1H, d, J 5.5 Hz, C_3 -H), 6.85–7.65 (9H, m, ArH); **3e** (65%) (i : ii 12 : 13); oil (Found : C, 73.2; H, 6.9; N, 3.3. $C_{24}H_{27}NO_5$ calcd. for : C, 73.5; H, 6.9; N, 3.5%; ν_{max} 1765 cm^{-1} (β -lactam CO); **3e(i)**, δ 1.20 (9H, m, $COOCH_2CH_3$, $CH(CH_3)_2$), 2.0 (1H, m, $CH(CH_3)_2$), 4.30 (3H, m, NCH, $COOCH_2CH_3$), 5.20 (1H, q, J 5.5 Hz, C_4 -H), 5.40 (1H, d, J 5.5 Hz, C_3 -H), 6.30–7.50 (13H, m, ArH, CH=CHAr); **3e(ii)**, δ 1.15 (9H, m, $COOCH_2CH_3$, $CH(CH_3)_2$), 2.30 (1H, m, $CH(CH_3)_2$), 4.25 (3H, m, NCH, $COOCH_2CH_3$), 4.9 (1H, q, J 5.5 Hz, C_4 -H), 5.40 (1H, d, J 5.5 Hz, C_3 -H), 6.35–7.50 (13H, m, ArH, CH=CHAr); **3g** (72%) (i : ii 11 : 9), m.p. 88–94° (Found : C, 70.6; H, 6.2; N, 4.0. $C_{20}H_{21}NO_4$ calcd. for : C, 70.7; H, 6.2; N, 4.1%; ν_{max} 1750 cm^{-1} (β -lactam CO); **3g(i)**, δ 1.27 (3H, t, $COOCH_2CH_3$), 1.72 (3H, d, CH_2CH_3), 41.2 (3H, m, NCH, $COOCH_2CH_3$), 5.05 (1H, d, J 5.5 Hz, C_4 -H), 5.40 (1H, d, J 5.5 Hz, C_3 -H), 6.70–7.45 (10H, m, ArH); **3g(ii)**, δ 1.25 (3H, t, $COOCH_2CH_3$), 1.72 (3H, d, CH_2CH_3), 4.22 (3H, q, NCH, CH_2CH_3), 5.20 (1H, d, J 5.5 Hz, C_4 -H), 5.42 (1H, d, J 5.5 Hz, C_3 -H), 6.82–7.53 (10H, m, ArH); **3h** (62%) (i : ii 3 : 2), m.p. 108–112° (Found : C, 70.34; H, 6.01; N, 3.2. $C_{28}H_{22}NO_6$ calcd. for : C, 71.03; H, 5.8; N, 2.95%; ν_{max} 1750 cm^{-1} (β -lactam CO); **3h(i)**, δ 0.83 (6H, m, $CH(CH_3)_2$), 2.0 (1H, m, $CH(CH_3)_2$), 3.8 (1H, d, J 7.5 Hz, CH), 5.0 (1H, d, J 4.5 Hz, C_4 -H), 5.16 (2H, s, OCH_2), 5.40 (1H, d, J 4.5 Hz, C_3 -H), 5.80 (2H, s, OCH_2O), 6.69–7.50 (3H, m, ArH); **3h(ii)**, δ 1.1 (6H, m, $CH(CH_3)_2$), 2.67 (1H, m, $CH(CH_3)_2$), 4.25 (1H, d, J 7.5 Hz, CH), 4.48 (1H, d, J 4.5 Hz, C_4 -H), 5.22 (2H, s, OCH_2), 5.4 (1H, d, J 4.5 Hz, C_3 -H), 5.98 (2H, s, OCH_2O), 6.67–7.72 (13H, m, ArH); **3i** (60%) (i : ii 3 : 2), m.p. 116–122° (Found : C, 72.74; H, 5.16; N, 2.9. $C_{32}H_{27}NO_6$ calcd. for : C, 73.7; H, 5.18; N, 2.68%; ν_{max} 1760 cm^{-1} (β -lactam CO); **3i(i)**, δ 3.1 (2H, d, $CHCH_2Ar$), 3.45 (1H, t, NCHCOO), 4.80 (1H, d, J 4.5 Hz, C_4 -H), 5.2 (2H, s, $COOCH_2Ar$), 5.3 (1H, d, J 4.5 Hz, C_3 -H), 5.90 (2H, s, OCH_2O), 6.30–7.50 (18H, m, ArH); **3i(ii)**, δ 3.0

(2H, d, CHCH₂Ar), 3.20 (1H, t, NCHCOO), 4.50 (1H, d, *J* 4.5 Hz, C₄-H), 4.62 (2H, s, COOCH₂Ar), 5.15 (1H, d, *J* 4.5 Hz, C₃-H), 5.90 (2H, s, OCH₂O), 6.30–7.50 (18H, m, ArH); **10** (65%) (i : ii 9 : 8), oil (Found : C, 55.9; H, 5.8; N, 3.8. C₁₆H₂₁NO₄S₂ calcd. for : C, 56.0; H, 5.9; N, 3.9%), ν_{\max} 1750 (ester CO), 1785 cm⁻¹ (β -lactam CO); **10(i)**, δ 1.35 (3H, t, COOCH₂CH₃), 1.85 (3H, d, CH(CH₃)₂), 2.35 (6H, s, 2*-SCH₃), 4.35 (3H, m, COOCH₂CH₃, CH), 5.30 (1H, s, C₃-H), 7.0–7.45 (5H, m, ArH); **10(ii)**, δ 1.35 (3H, t, COOCH₂CH₃), 1.75 (3H, d, CH-CH₃), 2.35 (6H, s, 2*-SCH₃), 4.35 (3H, m, COOCH₂CH₃, CH), 5.40 (1H, s, C₃-H), 7.0–7.45 (5H, m, ArH).

β -Lactam (3f) : A solution of POCl₃ (1.540 g, 0.01 mol) in dry dichloromethane (15 ml) was added dropwise to a well stirred mixture of imine **2f** (2.330 g, 0.01 mol), 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2.210 g, 0.01 mol) and triethylamine (2.220 g, 0.022 mol) in dry dichloromethane (75 ml) at low temperature (5–10°). The contents were stirred at room temperature for 10 h. The resulting solution was washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate (5%), then with brine. The organic layer was dried and evaporated under reduced pressure. The residual solid was submitted to chromatographic separation on neutral alumina using dichloromethane : ethyl acetate (8 : 2) as eluent to give **3f** as diastereomeric mixture of **3f(i)** and **3f(ii)**, (60%), m.p. 78–82° (Found : C, 57.5; H, 4.7; N, 2.7. C₂₃H₂₃NO₆Cl₂ calcd. for : C, 57.5; H, 4.7; N, 2.7%), ν_{\max} 1760 cm⁻¹ (β -lactam CO); **3f(i)**, δ 1.20 (9H, m, COOCH₂CH₃, CH(CH₃)₂), 2.10 (1H, m, CH(CH₃)₂), 4.15 (3H, m, NCH, COOCH₂CH₃), 5.30 (1H, d, *J* 5.5 Hz, C₄-H), 5.55 (1H, d, *J* 5.5 Hz, C₃-H), 6.05 (2H, s, OCH₂O), 6.85–7.55 (6H, m, ArH); **3f(ii)**, δ 1.20 (9H, m, COOCH₂CH₃, CH(CH₃)₂), 2.65 (1H, m, CH(CH₃)₂), 4.15 (3H, m, NCH, COOCH₂CH₃), 4.95 (1H, d, *J* 5.5 Hz, C₄-H), 5.55 (1H, d, *J* 5.5 Hz, C₃-H), 6.05 (2H, s, OCH₂O), 6.70–7.55 (6H, m, ArH).

β -Lactam 7 : Trimethylchlorosilane (0.986 g, 0.009 mol) was added dropwise to a well stirred mixture of imine **6** (2.0 g, 0.009 mol) and triethylamine (2.020 g, 0.02 mol) in

dry dichloromethane (35 ml) at low temperature. After stirring for 30 min, phenoxyacetyl chloride (1.538 g, 0.009 mol) was added dropwise at low temperature. The reaction mixture was stirred overnight at 25° and then stirred with methanol (2 ml) and water (10 ml) for 30 min. The organic layer was finally washed with brine and dried. Removal of solvent provided **7** (70%) which was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 134–136° (Found : C, 64.5; H, 6.8; N, 3.2. C₂₃H₂₉NO₅Si calcd. for C, 64.6; H, 6.8; N, 3.3%), ν_{\max} 1745 cm⁻¹ (β -lactam CO); **7(i)**, δ 0.1 (9H, d, Si(CH₃)₃), 0.90 (3H, t, CH₃), 1.55 (2H, m, C-CH₂), 3.70 (3H, m, NCH, CH₂O), 5.10 (1H, d, *J* 5.5 Hz, C₄-H), 5.60 (1H, d, *J* 5.5 Hz, C₃-H), 6.0 (2H, s, OCH₂O), 7.05–7.55 (8H, m, ArH); **7(ii)**, δ 0.1 (9H, d, Si(CH₃)₃), 0.90 (3H, t, CH₃), 1.55 (2H, m, C-CH), 3.70 (3H, m, N=CH, CH₂O), 5.15 (1H, d, *J* 5.5 Hz, C₄-H), 5.60 (1H, d, *J* 5.5 Hz, C₃-H), 6.0 (2H, s, OCH₂O), 7.05–7.55 (8H, m, ArH).

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